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for detecting fin and blue whale calls: Application to onshore
seismometers in eastern Canada, 2023**

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Abstract

This report presents a method and Python code for detecting band-limited, regularly-repeating signals in seismic or hydrophone data. The method is designed to target stereotyped “20 Hz” calls of both fin and blue whales that are common in the western North Atlantic. In addition to the core functionality of the detector, the Python package also includes functions to download seismic data from public data centers, as well as plotting and cataloging detection results. Many parameters of the detection function can be easily customized to target different populations of fin or blue whales, but default parameters are provided that target western North Atlantic populations. We applied the code to one year (2023) of data from 21 onshore seismometers in eastern Canada, including the Lower St. Lawrence Seaway, Atlantic Canada, and the eastern Arctic. We observe false detections at some stations and discuss limitations of the detection algorithm. We report the first observation of fin and blue whale calls at CHEG in Chéticamp, NS on the eastern Gulf of St. Lawrence, as well as fin whale calls on GGN in Saint-George, NB near the mouth of the Bay of Fundy.

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1 Introduction

Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) is an important tool that researchers use to monitor baleen whales, including fin whales (*Balaenoptera physalus*; e.g. [Roy et al., 2018](#); [Davis et al., 2020](#)) and blue whales (*Balaenoptera musculus*; e.g. [Lesage et al., 2018](#); [Wingfield et al., 2022](#)). [Plourde and Nedimović \(2022\)](#) found that onshore seismometers, designed for monitoring earthquakes, near Lower St. Lawrence Estuary and broader Gulf of St. Lawrence routinely record fin whale calls (A notes) and blue whale calls (type A, B, or A-B) with frequencies near 20 Hz. They introduced a detection algorithm that relies on the regular internote interval (INI) of these 20 Hz calls and used it to build a catalog of detections spanning 2015–2020. [Goblot et al. \(2024a\)](#) then extended this to January 2022 for the same region, although several of the seismometers examined by [Plourde and Nedimović \(2022\)](#) were not active for those years. The detection algorithm of these studies was implemented in MATLAB, and was made publicly available on Zenodo by [Goblot et al. \(2024b\)](#).

This report presents a Python package of the method implemented in a more user-friendly manner, including default parameters that target the western North Atlantic populations of fin and blue whales, while allowing customization to target other populations with (for example) distinct INI from those in the North Atlantic. We apply this new code to 21 seismometers across the Lower St. Lawrence Seaway, elsewhere in Atlantic Canada, and the eastern Canadian Arctic, from 2023. Note that most of the seismometers have a network code of CN; PCAQ is the exception with a network code of C8. Network codes will appear in most tables and figures but for brevity CN will usually be omitted in the text.

Figure 1. Maps of CNSN seismometers included in this analysis, divided into (a) southern, and (b) northern regions. The color bathymetry scale is shared. Seismometers plotted in light green are those on which fin and/or blue whales were detected in 2023; seismometers in darker red had no confirmed detections.

The seismometers used in this study (Fig. 1) have three orthogonal geophones, two horizontal and one vertical, oriented such that positive velocities point to east, north, and up. All data used in this study were recorded at 100 sps. More information about the seismometers is available from the International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks (FDSN; [Geological Survey of Canada, 1975, 2002](#)). Instrument response was removed prior to analyses in this report; this should not generally affect the detection algorithm, although it allows waveforms to be plotted with a physical unit (m s^{-1}).

2 Method

Here we outline the double-spectrogram method for detecting fin or blue whale calls at a seismometer. The method has many parameters that can be adjusted to target the frequencies and INI specific to a given species or population, with default values for fin and blue whales in the western North Atlantic listed in Table 1.

1. Zero-phase bandpass filter waveforms from a single seismometer between a range $[f_{\min}, f_{\max}]$ (Figure 2a,e). We typically apply the method to data saved in 24-hour-long files, but any length of data stream longer than a detection window duration $t_{\text{win},2}$ can be used.
2. Compute power spectrograms $P_{[E,N,Z]}(t, f)$ for each component (east, north, up) using window duration $t_{\text{win},1}$ spaced with a fractional overlap of r_1 . Sum to obtain $P_1(t, f)$ (Figure 2b,f). Apply Gaussian smoothing to the spectrogram in the time and frequency dimensions using standard deviations σ_t and σ_f , respectively; note that these are not scaled to the physical unit and instead refer to a number of samples.
3. Compute the whale call index ([Širović et al., 2015](#); [Pilkington et al., 2018](#)) by summing power from frequencies expected to contain whale calls (the target band; Figure 2b,f):

$$C(t) = \sum_{f_a}^{f_b} P_1(t, f), \quad (1)$$

as well as a ratio with power in frequency bands adjacent to the target band in the denominator (Figure 2c,g):

$$R(t) = \frac{C(t)}{\sum_{f_{\min}}^{f_a - \Delta f_a} P_1(t, f) + \sum_{f_b + \Delta f_b}^{f_{\max}} P_1(t, f)}. \quad (2)$$

4. Compute a secondary power spectrogram $P_2(t, T)$, from either $C(t)$ (default) or $R(t)$, using window duration $t_{\text{win},2}$. Zero overlap between windows is applied by default, but there is an available fractional overlap parameter r_2 . We refer to period (T) instead of frequency here for the convenience of using INI values in the range of ~ 10 to 100 s periods.
5. Compute the ratio $W(t)$ from $P_2(t, T)$ as the sum of energy near the characteristic INI divided by the sum of energy at adjacent periods, specifically:

$$W(t) = \frac{\sum_{T_a}^{T_b} P_2(t, T)}{\sum_{T_{\min}}^{T_a - \Delta T_a} P_2(t, T) + \sum_{T_b + \Delta T_b}^{T_{\max}} P_2(t, T)}. \quad (3)$$

A high $W(t)$ is used to indicate the presence of repeating whale calls (Figure 2d,h). Note that $P_1(t, T)$, $C(t)$, $R(t)$ will have a sample rate controlled by $t_{\text{win},1}$ and r_1 , whereas $P_2(t, T)$ and $W(t)$ will have a much lower sample rate controlled by $t_{\text{win},2}$ and r_2 .

- Identify individual calls by recursively selecting the maximum from $R(t)$ that is at least $t_{\min_call_sep}$ away from previous selections. Maxima must meet several criteria: i) they must exceed $a_{R,win}$ times a rolling median of $R(t)$, computed with a window length of $t_{win,2}$, ii) they must exceed the median of the entire $R(t)$ by $a_{R,win}$ times its median absolute deviation, iii) they must be in a window with $W(t) > W_{\min}$, and iv) they must meet a minimum signal-to-noise ratio ($SNR > SNR_{\min}$). Continue until no remaining $R(t)$ meet these criteria. Compute the SNR of each call as $SNR = 10 \log_{10}(\frac{P_{\text{signal}}}{P_{\text{noise}}})$, where P_{signal} is measured from a window of duration $t_{SNR,signal}$ centered on the selected local maximum of $R(t)$, and P_{noise} is measured from window of duration $t_{SNR,noise}$ that ends $t_{SNR,buffer}$ before the signal window. P_{signal} and P_{noise} are signal power measurements normalized for window duration.

Figure 2. Example fin whale detection (left) and blue whale detection (right) from station PMAQ. Note that these fin and blue whale songs overlap in time; two of the identified blue whale calls are visible on the left spectrogram and fin whale calls are visible on the right spectrogram. **(a,e)** Three-component seismograms, bandpass filtered to the target band of the given species. **(b,f)** Spectrograms of the same waveform segments, with a solid green line highlighting the target band and dashed red lines highlighting the adjacent bands used in the denominator of $R(t)$. **(c,g)** $R(t)$ computed from the spectrograms, with calls labeled by red lines and their SNR in dB. **(d,h)** Periodogram of $R(t)$ with the periods used in the numerator of $W(t)$ highlighted in green, and those from the denominator highlighted in red.

Note that because we depend on the periodicity of $C(t)$ or $R(t)$ to trigger detections, we are assuming that only one whale is audible at once (in the target frequency band), or at least that the signal is not saturated with whale calls, as has been observed to occur sometimes on hydrophone data (e.g. [Pilkington et al., 2018](#)). [Schleimer et al. \(2019\)](#) surveyed for fin whales in the LSLs and recorded a median group size of only 1–2, although this does not preclude multiple groups being within the detection radius of a given seismometer at once, and [Plourde and Nedimović \(2022\)](#) did find examples of two fin whales singing at once on one

seismometer.

The Python package also includes tools to tally detections and calls per day, including classifying days as “active” or “passive”, that is discussed in Section 3.2. It closely follows the related section of [Plourde and Nedimović \(2022\)](#), including using the same thresholds by default. Details of these tools are described by in-code comments.

Figure 3. Example single-call figure for a fin whale call from Figure 2, showing the same call in **(top)** a spectrogram, **(middle)** three-component seismogram, and **(bottom)** particle-motion traces in the E–N, Z–N, and E–Z planes. The timescale varies from 120 s for the spectrogram, to 6 s for the seismogram, and to 1.2 s for the particle-motion traces, with the shorter windows highlighted on the previous plot (around Time = 0). On the spectrogram, calls are indicated by dashed red lines and their SNR in dB. The seismograms further highlights the central 1.2 s window with a color gradation that is shared with the particle-motion traces. Particle-motion is scaled relative to the labeled maximum amplitude.

Table 1. A list of parameters defined in this section with columns to indicate their corresponding name in the Python code, their physical unit, and default values for fin and blue whales within the Python code.

<i>Parameters for double-spectrogram method.</i>				
Parameter	Name in Code	Unit	Default (Fin)	Default (Blue)
f_{\min}	freqmin_1	Hz	10.0	8.0
f_{\max}	freqmax_1	Hz	32.0	32.0
$t_{\text{win},1}$	window_dur_1	s	1.0	2.0
r_1	overlap_1	-	0.5	0.5
σ_t	sigma_time	samples	1	1
σ_f	sigma_freq	samples	1	1
f_a	target_band_1[0]	Hz	18.0	16.0
f_b	target_band_1[1]	Hz	21.0	19.0
Δf_a	freq_buffer_low	Hz	1.0	1.0
Δf_b	freq_buffer_high	Hz	1.5	1.25
$t_{\text{win},2}$	window_dur_2	s	120.0	720.0
r_2	overlap_2	-	0	0
T_a	target_band_2[0]	s	9.0	60.0
T_b	target_band_2[1]	s	15.0	80.0
T_{\min}	T_min_2	s	7.0	40.0
T_{\max}	T_max_2	s	65.0	205.0
ΔT_a	T_buffer_low	s	0.5	1.5
ΔT_b	T_buffer_high	s	0.75	2.0
<i>Parameters for identifying individual calls.</i>				
Parameter	Name in Code	Unit	Default (Fin)	Default (Blue)
$t_{\min_call_sep}$	min_call_separation	s	5.0	45.0
$a_{R,\text{win}}$	min_power_multiplier	-	2.0	2.0
$a_{R,\text{mad}}$	min_N_MAD_R	-	3.0	3.0
W_{\min}	min_W_for_calls	-	1.4	1.0
$t_{\text{SNR},\text{signal}}$	snr_signal_window_dur	s	1.0	4.0
$t_{\text{SNR},\text{noise}}$	snr_noise_window_dur	s	3.0	15.0
$t_{\text{SNR},\text{buffer}}$	snr_noise_window_buffer	s	1.0	8.0
SNR_{\min}	min_call_snr	dB	0.5	0.5
ΔSNR_{\max}	max_call_snr_difference	dB	5.0	5.0

<i>Other functions and quantities that appear in algorithm/code.</i>			
<i>*Units assume that the input stream is a velocity seismogram ($m s^{-1}$).</i>			
Parameter	Name in Code	Unit*	Description
$P_1(t, f)$	spec_1	$(m s^{-1})^2$	Spectrogram of input waveforms.
$C(t)$	target_band_power	$(m s^{-1})^2$	Whale call index.
$R(t)$	power_ratio_1	-	Ratio of power in the frequency-band of whale calls over adjacent bands.
$P_2(t, T)$	spec_2	$(m s^{-1})^4$	Second spectrogram, of $C(t)$ or $R(t)$. Note it will be unitless if $R(t)$ is input.
$W(t)$	power_ratio_2	-	Double-spectrogram ratio; energy in target INI over energy in adjacent period bands.

3 Python Code

This report presents an implementation of the method in pure Python; all of its dependencies are publicly available and are listed in the `__init__.py` file along with installation recommendations. The package has been tested primarily by running Python 3.11 in Ubuntu 22 via Windows Subsystem for Linux, and although the vast majority of functionality should translate seamlessly across operating systems, this has not been thoroughly tested.

3.1 Double Spectrogram Detector

An example script to download one station-day of seismic data (via tools in ObsPy; [Krischer et al., 2015](#)) and run the detector for both fin and blue whales (using default parameters) is presented in Code 1; the output of which should include the plots of Figures 2 and 3. Input seismic or hydrophone data does not need to be downloaded from an FDSN server or via ObsPy, but it does need to be readable to an ObsPy `Stream` and certain metadata in the `Stream` must be complete (start- and end-times, sample rate, and network, station, location, and channel codes). The example script saves seismic data in Seismic Analysis Code (SAC) format ([Goldstein and Snoke, 2005](#)).

Code 1: Script to download one station-day of seismic data (from CNSN station PMAQ), initialize detection-parameter objects, run the detector, and write the results (main detector and individual calls) to text files. Note that the keyword argument `plot_power_threshold` and `figure_save_directory` are included to save detection figures such as those in Figure 2. Three additional keyword arguments enable individual calls with high-SNR to be plotted (Figure 3); this is not recommended for blue whale calls. Note that if re-running the detector on the same data downloading and saving the seismic data can be skipped, and instead be read in with `stream = obspy.read('*PMAQ*.SAC')` after importing ObsPy.

```
1 import WhaleSeis as WS
2
3 stream = WS.download_test_data()
4
5 fin_param = WS.FinWhaleDetectorParameters()
6 blue_param = WS.BlueWhaleDetectorParameters()
7
8 fin_output = WS.double_spectrogram_detector(stream,
9                                             fin_param, plot_power_threshold=5.0,
10                                            plot_call_snr_threshold=10.0,
11                                            plot_call_power_threshold=5.0,
12                                            max_calls_to_plot=10,
13                                            figure_save_directory='FinWhaleFigures/')
14 fin_output.write_power_ratios()
15 fin_output.write_calls()
16
17 blue_output = WS.double_spectrogram_detector(stream,
18                                             blue_param, plot_power_threshold=6.0,
19                                             figure_save_directory='BlueWhaleFigures/')
20 blue_output.write_power_ratios()
21 blue_output.write_calls()
```

Keyword arguments can be used to tailor selected detection parameters, as exemplified in Code 2. This example only alters a few parameters; a non-exhaustive list of important parameters (and keyword argu-

ments) is in Table 1, whereas a more complete description of the available parameters is found in the comments of `DoubleSpectrogramDetectorParameters` class (and child classes for fin and blue whales) in `detector_parameters.py`.

Code 2: In this call of `FinWhaleDetectorParameters()` a higher target frequency band is used to look for calls centered at ~ 25 Hz, and a corresponding increase to the maximum frequency included in the spectrogram (f_{\max} , `freqmax_1`) is applied. In addition, Gaussian smoothing of the spectrogram is disabled by setting `sigma_time` and `sigma_freq` to zero. Note that `WhaleSeis` is assumed to be imported as `WS` in the remaining Code examples.

```
1 fin_param = WS.FinWhaleDetectorParameters(target_band_1=[22.0, 28.0],
2                                           freqmax_1=45.0,
3                                           sigma_time=0,
4                                           sigma_freq=0)
```

The output of `double_spectrogram_detector()` is a custom-class object, `DoubleSpectrogramDetectorOutput`, that stores $W(t)$ as `power_ratios`, the start time of each window in $W(t)$ as `window_start_times`, an INI for each window interpolated as the peak of $P_2(t, T)$ as `peak_periods`, as well similar variables to store the individual call detections, and the input parameters (in `parameters`). It also has built-in methods to write the detector results and calls to text files (Code 3); by default, the file names contain the stream network, station, and location codes, the date of its start time, the species specified in the detector parameters, and either `_power` for the $W(t)$ values or `_calls` for individual calls.

Code 3: In this call of `write_power_ratios()` and `write_calls()` for fin whale detection results, a custom filename and path to the file save location are input. This snippet imagines we are looping over Julian days, years, and stations and assumes `station`, `year`, and `julday` are defined strings.

```
1 fin_output.write_power_ratios(
2     path='YOUR_FOLDER/Detections/'+year+'/' + julday+'/',
3     filename=station+'.' + year+'.' + julday+'.Fin_Detections.txt')
4 fin_output.write_calls(
5     path='YOUR_FOLDER/Calls/'+year+'/' + julday+'/',
6     filename=station+'.' + year+'.' + julday+'.Fin_Calls.txt')
```

3.2 Quality Control

By default, `double_spectrogram_detector()` will run several data quality-control checks on the input waveforms:

1. `quality_check_gaps()`. This function checks for gaps in the waveform data; it flags windows (those associated with $P_2(t, T)$ and $W(t)$) that contain any waveform data that is equal to precisely zero (other than the first and last samples, which are permitted to equal zero). Periods of zeroes are not likely to contribute to false detections, but it is important to flag times the station was not operational.
2. `quality_check_spikes()`. This function checks for elements in the waveforms with absolute value greater than a_{spike} (`spike_quality_threshold`, 500.0 by default) times the median absolute value, and flags windows where they exist. Large spikes could be due to natural signals (e.g.

earthquakes), anthropogenic noise, or instrumental noise; in any case they are likely to interfere with whale call detection.

3. `quality_check_sinusoidal()`. This function flags windows where $W(t)$ is high ($> W_{\min}$), but there is lower energy than expected for periods associated with harmonics of the INI (e.g. see the peaks near 6, 4, and 3 second periods in Figure 2d). If there is a lack of power at these shorter periods, it indicates a more sinusoidal fluctuation of energy in the target band $[T_a, T_b]$, rather than relatively brief calls with regular INI; sinusoidal fluctuations are more likely associated to anthropogenic or instrument noise. This check therefore measures energy within `short_period_band` and ensures that it is both reasonably low compared to the target band (Equation 3, numerator) and reasonably high compared to the "control band" of $W(t)$ (Equation 3, denominator). These thresholds are set by `target_short_ratio_threshold` (6.0 by default) and `short_period_threshold` (0.5 by default), respectively.

Unless these checks are all disabled, `double_spectrogram_detector()` will run the an internal method `clean_detections()` on the `DoubleSpectrogramDetectorOutput` object, giving it new versions of its key properties with `_culled` appended to the names (e.g. `power_ratios_culled`). These new versions contain only data from windows that did not pass the quality checks, and these windows are removed from the original versions.

3.3 Detection Database

The `WhaleDetectionDatabase` class has functions for reading the text files output by `double_spectrogram_detector`, tallying detections and calls per day, and plotting the number of detections per day. There are several customizable parameters to determine what constitutes a detection/call, including:

1. `threshold_W`. A minimum double-spectrogram ratio $W(t)$ to be considered a detection. Defaults are $W(t) = 3$ for fin whales, or 1.5 for blue whales.
2. `threshold_snr`. A minimum SNR for a call to be considered a valid. Default = 1.0 dB.
3. `min_calls_per_detection`. A minimum number of calls (meeting the threshold SNR) in the window for a detection to be considered valid. Defaults = 6 for fin whales, 5 for blue whales.

There are additional parameters to decide whether a station is considered "On" or "Off" on a given day, meaning whether there is data that was not flagged by quality-control checks for a sufficient portion of the day, as well as whether the day is "active" or "passive".

4. `min_portion_of_day`. Default = 0.75.
5. `min_detections_active_day`. Defaults = 5 for fin whales, 3 for blue whales.

Active days have a sufficient number of detections that they are assumed to be robust (because fin and blue whale songs tend to persist for longer than a single detection), and the relatively few detections on quiet days are assumed to be spurious. A day must be labeled "On" to be classified as "active" or "passive". All thresholds can be set for specific stations within the database, but by default the same thresholds will apply to all stations (they are found in `whale_detection_database_default_thresholds.py`).

Code 4: An example of how a database (in this case for fin whale detections) can be created with one command, followed by commands to plot numbers of detections per day in histogram-style and heat-map-style figures, of which there are examples in the Results section. The specified folder is searched, including in recursively through sub-folders, for detection results (both `_power` and `_calls` files). This assumes the default file-naming structure was used when saving detector results. Alternatively, rather than a `data_folder`, a `list_of_detection_files` and `list_of_call_files` can be specified.

```
1 fin_database = WS.WhaleDetectionDatabase (  
2     data_folder='/path_to_folder/FinWhaleDetectionResults/')  
3 fin_database.plot_database ()  
4 fin_database.plot_heat_map ()
```

If all the detection and call files reside for a given dataset (and a given species) reside in a parent folder, a database can be created with a single command (Code 4). Data can also be added to a database after it is created with the internal `add_data()` function. Internal functions also exist for plotting results; example figures produced by `plot_heat_map()` are presented in the Results section. `plot_database()` produces histogram-style plots that are not shown in this report.

4 Results

Fin and blue whale detections per day at each seismometer (station) are shown with color-scale “heat maps” in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. As in *Plourde and Nedimović (2022)*, we assign 5 detections per day as the fin-whale active-day threshold, and 3 detections per day as the blue-whale active-day threshold. Days with fewer detections than these thresholds are labeled “quiet” and their detections are assumed to be spurious. After visual inspection of active-day detections, several stations were deemed not to have true detections; these stations are indicated in Figures 4 and 5.

Examples of false detections are shown in Figure 6. The spectrogram in Figure 6a resembles fin whale A notes, although the notes appear as upsweeps, rather than the typical downsweep. SJNN is in northern St. John’s, NL and is ~500 m south of a concrete/aggregate business, and its detections are limited to daytime hours in the summer, so it seems very likely that these signals relate to machinery, e.g. a crusher. The remaining detections noise bands that sinusoidal or semi-continuous; the example at SNFQ (Figure 6b) did not actually register as a detection due to the `quality_check_sinusoidal` function. These noise bands resemble observations of ship noise on hydrophones (e.g. *McKenna et al., 2012; Gloza, 2011*), but we cannot confidently assess their origins.

Seven stations exceeded the fin-whale active-day threshold at least once: C8.PCAQ, CHEG, CNOQ, GGN, ICQ, PMAQ, and SMQ (Table 2). For blue whales there were also seven stations with at least 1 active day, but with one substitution: C8.PCAQ, BJBQ, CHEG, CNOQ, ICQ, PMAQ, and SMQ (Table 3). To tally total numbers of detections and calls across all stations, we ignore those previously invalidated stations, but otherwise consider active-day detections to be valid and quiet-day detections to be false. Given these assumptions, there are 1182 fin whale detections with 9846 total calls, across 7 stations. For blue whales, there are 2462 detections and 19547 calls, across 7 stations.

No detections were observed in the Arctic or ar stations HAL, GBN, or SJNN close to the open continental shelf. However, both fin and blue whales were observed on CHEG in Chéticamp, NS on the eastern Gulf of St. Lawrence (Figure 7), and fin whales were observed at GGN in Saint-George, NB near the mouth of the Bay of Fundy (Figure 8). Note that BJBQ and CNOQ were not previously reported on, but they essentially replaced NATG and CNQ, respectively, on which *Plourde and Nedimović (2022)* observed both species.

Figure 4. Fin whale detections per day. Red lines indicate days where no data was available or the day was labeled “Off” after quality control. Stations highlighted in *red italics* were deemed not to have any robust detections after visual inspection.

Figure 5. Blue whale detections per day (see Figure 4 figure for description).

Figure 6. Examples of erroneous “detections”. Three examples come from the fin whale detector, at stations: **(a)** SJNN, **(b)** SNFQ, and **(c)** CLRN. **(d)** A erroneous blue whale detection at FRB. See Figure 2 for descriptions of each panel.

Table 2. Summary of fin whale detection results. Stations highlighted in *red italics* were deemed not to have any robust detections after visual inspection.

Station	Days		Active Days (≥ 5 Det.)				Quiet Days (< 5 Det.)			
	On	Off	Days	Det.	Calls	SNR	Days	Det.	Calls	SNR
C8.PCAQ	365	0	1	13	112	7.81	364	41	333	7.57
CN.A16	362	3	0	0	0	-	362	14	95	3.98
CN.A21	365	0	0	0	0	-	365	4	27	3.23
CN.A61	364	1	0	0	0	-	364	19	136	5.22
CN.BJBQ	365	0	0	0	0	-	365	25	174	5.90
CN.CACQ	365	0	0	0	0	-	365	22	161	5.58
CN.CHEG	365	0	1	9	81	5.48	364	17	126	5.86
<i>CN.CLRN</i>	364	1	<i>4</i>	<i>24</i>	<i>173</i>	<i>2.66</i>	360	115	831	2.75
CN.CNOQ	365	0	2	30	241	7.02	363	192	1389	5.17
CN.FRB	365	0	0	0	0	-	365	14	100	5.39
CN.GBN	365	0	0	0	0	-	365	9	57	3.22
CN.GGN	363	2	2	26	262	4.91	361	40	273	5.29
<i>CN.HAL</i>	364	1	<i>3</i>	<i>23</i>	<i>173</i>	<i>3.08</i>	361	188	1397	3.05
CN.ICQ	364	1	10	225	1890	6.01	354	41	278	3.10
CN.ILON	358	7	0	0	0	-	358	20	135	2.56
CN.PMAQ	164	0	34	857	7014	5.26	130	86	624	3.71
<i>CN.POIN</i>	362	3	<i>1</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>32</i>	<i>2.71</i>	361	19	134	4.30
CN.SAKN	34	0	0	0	0	-	34	3	26	3.80
<i>CN.SJNN</i>	365	0	<i>48</i>	<i>3414</i>	<i>32690</i>	<i>11.26</i>	317	121	865	4.64
CN.SMQ	358	7	4	31	246	4.93	354	26	181	3.04
CN.SNFQ	363	2	0	0	0	-	363	7	50	4.08
Totals			53	1182	9846					

Table 3. Summary of blue whale detection results. Stations highlighted in *red italics* were deemed not to have any robust detections after visual inspection.

Station	Days		Active Days (≥ 3 Det.)				Quiet Days (< 3 Det.)			
	On	Off	Days	Det.	Calls	SNR	Days	Det.	Calls	SNR
C8.PCAQ	363	2	9	60	481	6.12	354	56	390	5.21
CN.A16	360	5	0	0	0	-	360	43	302	5.90
CN.A21	365	0	0	0	0	-	365	78	563	6.25
CN.A61	364	1	0	0	0	-	364	66	442	5.13
CN.BJBQ	365	0	16	229	1925	5.89	349	52	365	4.03
CN.CACQ	365	0	0	0	0	-	365	57	382	3.82
CN.CHEG	365	0	18	121	870	2.76	347	74	500	4.63
CN.CLRN	362	3	0	0	0	-	362	23	156	5.96
CN.CNOQ	365	0	2	7	43	5.18	363	30	246	4.62
<i>CN.FRB</i>	365	0	<i>10</i>	<i>41</i>	<i>259</i>	<i>2.48</i>	355	130	901	5.83
<i>CN.GBN</i>	365	0	<i>4</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>87</i>	<i>2.97</i>	361	93	660	5.33
CN.GGN	363	2	0	0	0	-	363	35	254	5.06
<i>CN.HAL</i>	364	1	<i>5</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>97</i>	<i>2.55</i>	359	108	766	2.98
CN.ICQ	364	1	58	909	7021	3.27	306	77	524	2.40
CN.ILON	354	11	0	0	0	-	354	20	129	4.13
CN.PMAQ	164	0	58	832	6925	5.06	106	48	327	4.74
<i>CN.POIN</i>	364	1	<i>1</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>8.06</i>	363	84	592	5.02
CN.SAKN	34	0	0	0	0	-	34	5	41	3.77
CN.SJNN	365	0	0	0	0	-	365	104	755	4.67
CN.SMQ	357	8	40	304	2282	3.31	317	59	386	3.21
CN.SNFQ	364	1	0	0	0	-	364	25	179	7.16
Totals			199	2462	19547					

Figure 7. Fin whale (left) and blue detections (right) on CHEG. See Figure 2 for a description of each sub-figure.

Figure 8. Fin whale detection on GGN. See Figure 2 for a description of each sub-figure.

5 Discussion and Conclusions

This report presents some improvements to the double-spectrogram method for detecting fin and blue whale “20 Hz” calls common in the western North Atlantic. The method is implemented in a Python package that we hope is relatively straightforward for future researchers to implement and build upon. This study highlighted some limitations of the double-spectrogram method, with false “detections”, according to simple $W(t)$ thresholds, being common on certain seismometers, particularly those in the Arctic. We speculate that many of the false detections are associated with ship noise.

Collectively, *Plourde and Nedimović (2022)*, *Goblots et al. (2024a)*, and this study provide a catalog of seismic fin and blue whale detections for St. Lawrence Estuary and Gulf spanning late 2015 to 2023, but with a gap in 2022. The detector was also applied to 14 seismometers for the first time, including stations in New Brunswick, Nova Scotia, Newfoundland, Labrador, and Nunavut. A majority of these, including all seismometers in the Arctic, did not record any robust detections. However, we report the first observation of fin and blue whale calls at CHEG in Chéticamp, NS on the eastern Gulf of St. Lawrence, as well as fin whale calls on GGN in Saint-George, NB near the mouth of the Bay of Fundy. These are the first observations of whale calls at onshore seismometers outside the Estuary and western Gulf of St. Lawrence.

The total number of fin whale calls observed in 2023 is lower than the annual rate observed by *Plourde and Nedimović (2022)*. A direct comparison between years is complicated because there have been several changes in the seismometer network in the timespan of late 2015 to 2023. Most notably, LESQ, which had over half on the fin whale detections and calls from the *Plourde and Nedimović (2022)* dataset, stopped operating in mid-2019. LESQ was relatively westward, up-estuary, near the mouth of the Saguenay River, where a variety of monitoring efforts have observed a high fin-whale presence (*Martins et al., 2022*). However, CACQ is relatively close to LESQ and has operated since 2018, and saw no fin whale detections in 2023 despite having hundreds in 2018 and 2019. This suggests that fin whale A-note vocalizations were less abundant in the Estuary in 2023 than in 2016–2019.

The total numbers of blue whale detections in 2023, as well as their spatial distribution, are similar to previously analyzed years, with ICQ and PMAQ remaining the most active stations.

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